

AUDIT HISTORY

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Abstract. This article examines the historical stages of the audit development. The evolutionary development of audit in the civilization of economics and the audit controversy.

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The history of auditing in the Ancient World

The concept of audit comes from the Latin word "audire", which means "to hear", that is, to understand the ongoing process, phenomenon and be able to evaluate it.

The formation and history of the audit goes back centuries: the earliest confirmed reports of the auditor were Babylonian clay tablets that existed about 5000 years ago. The first auditor in the world may have created tiny signs on clay tablets next to the inventory lines. During the time of the Kingdom of the Nile, a representative of the pharaoh supervised the storage of grain. The audit function was to repeat the work done earlier by other persons. The systems were very simple, and the audit consisted of observing, calculating and rechecking the report. Of particular interest is the development of audit in China. Some researchers believe that it was in China that the audit system was first created (in 700 BC), which was sufficiently developed in the XIV century (under the Yuan Dynasty).

In ancient Greece and Rome, the audit took on a more distinct shape. In the 5th century BC, in Athens, the people's Assembly controlled the revenues and expenditures of the state, and in the Roman Republic, public finances were controlled by the Senate and a staff of auditors. It is here that special regulatory

bodies appear, whose duty it has become to monitor the correctness of maintaining accounting documents. The quaestors, as the "employees" of such services were called, sent their reports to Rome for hearing.

The first mention of audit as a kind of professional activity in Western civilization dates back to the XIII and XIV centuries, when accounting books compiled by merchants began to appear as material evidence in court. Since the XVI century, legal control of accounting books has been introduced in many countries and the term "auditor" has been used to refer to people who are engaged in checking accounts. Historically, the emergence of audit refers to the period of the formation of accounting as a branch of special scientific knowledge. We find evidence of this in the first work of the Italian scientist Luca Pacioli – "Treatise and accounts and records". They are found later in fiction, which characterizes audit as a social phenomenon. Thus, William Shakespeare in his play "Timon of Athens" says the following about the role of auditors through the mouth of Flavius:

Since you doubted my honesty
Or in the ability to conduct business,
Call the strictest intermediaries,
To test me.

The world's first audit. The earliest independent audit (in its modern sense) was carried out in 1720 by Charles Snell as a result of the scandal with the "South Sea Company" in England, which was called the "South Sea soap bubble".

The history of modern audit in Europe and the USA

When an audit is considered from a modern perspective, it is linked, first of all, with the development of joint-stock companies, when property was separated from the government, and the owners of capital began to hire specialists (managers,

administrators) to manage it directly. The shareholders themselves assumed the functions of capital flow control. In this part, the audit has become the companion of a professional manager, and the auditor is an independent expert who must objectively assess the economic situation at the enterprise. It should be noted that the development of joint-stock companies was the impetus for the development of audit. Under these conditions, the audit has assumed a certain social and public function, providing an objective judgment on the reliability of the reporting data provided by joint-stock companies in order to reduce the information risk of their partners.

The birthplace of professional audit is considered to be the United Kingdom. The industrial Revolution in England led to the creation of production structures funded by shareholders. This situation has created a need for auditors, both external and internal. To protect the public, the British Companies Act of 1844 introduced a procedure for mandatory audit of joint-stock companies. Soon after, in 1853, organizations of highly qualified chartered accountants were formed in Scotland.

In Germany, the first attempt to introduce an audit was made in 1870, when the supervisory boards of joint-stock companies had to check the main reporting forms — the balance sheet and the profit distribution report-and report on the results of the audit at general meetings of shareholders.

The legal date of the emergence of the modern institute of audit can be considered 1862, when the Law on Mandatory Audit was issued in England. Following England, similar laws were adopted in France (1867) and in Germany (1870), where they were considered as a direct continuation of the Law on Joint-Stock Companies. At the same time, in France, the audit was immediately assigned

to two organizations: the Association of Expert Accountants, who created the Chamber of Expert Accountants, and the Association of Verified Accountants and the Society of Commissioners Authorized for Accounts. The main difference between them was that the former were invited, and the latter were appointed. The activities of the commissioners of accounts were strictly regulated by representative bodies, and it was they who were entrusted with monitoring the use of budget funds.

The British were not only the founders of modern auditing, but also laid the foundations of professional auditing in the United States. Historically, the American audit originated in some US states and was conducted by specialists who received education and received practical training in the UK. At the end of the XIX century, American companies invited British auditors from the companies "Price Waterhouse", "Peat Marwick & Company" and "Arthur Young & Company". One of the first key events in the history of the American audit community was the establishment in 1887 of an organization that was the predecessor of the American Institute of Certified Independent Accountants (AICPA).

A special impetus to the development of the audit business was given by the world economic crisis of 1929-1932, when the mass bankruptcy of joint-stock companies and enterprises required tightening the procedure and approval of their reports and balance sheets by independent auditors. As a reaction to the crisis, the New York Stock Exchange in 1933 issued rules requiring the audit of companies whose shares were listed on the stock exchange. Since the mid-30s. In the XX century, almost all developed countries are beginning to introduce mandatory requirements for the amount of information that must be contained in annual reports, published and the reliability of which must be confirmed by professional

auditors. In 1937, the Law on Mandatory Audit in the United States was adopted, which later became a model in the world audit.

Thus, summing up the above, it can be stated that the emergence and development of modern audit was caused by the separation of the interests of those who are directly involved in the management of the organization (administration, managers), and those who invest money in its activities (owners, shareholders, investors, creditors, etc.).

Stages of development of audit activity

The first period (until 1850). Initially, there was a control that was carried out from top to bottom. The controller was the " eyes and ears " of the boss, with the help of which the work of subordinates was monitored.

This was an ongoing control: the performer works, the controller observes and immediately, if necessary, collects. Then there was a follow-up control. Its forms were very simple. For example, an official who had access to material values stole some of them. The recovery of stolen property in the West and in Russia was carried out in different ways.

In the West, if an official became rich, they brought him to court and often confiscated all his property, returning it to the treasury. In Russia, things were simpler: a big official, say a voivode, was appointed to a position. He was not paid a salary, because he was officially enrolled "for feeding". After three or four years of service, this voivode was transferred (usually in winter) to a new place, where he went with his accumulated belongings, and the control authorities ambushed the wagon train along the way and took away all the carts, except for one. This is how the subsequent control was carried out.

Much later, control began to acquire more civilized forms, real controllers appeared, i.e. people who performed functions that are inherent in control today. The main methods of verification were a detailed study of exculpatory documents and an inventory.

Audit as one of the forms of economic control appeared in England. Written monuments indicating its existence date back to the XIII-XIV centuries. It is known that in 1324, by Royal Decree, John de Pakesley and two of his comrades were appointed to audit the counties of Oxford, Berkshire, South Empton, Wilts, Samset and Dorset.

Since the XIII century, a new one has been distinguished from the general concept of "accounting employee" – "auditor". The former retained the functions of organization and accounting in its daily activities, and the latter was entrusted with the functions of an independent controller checking accounting accounts.

In the regulatory document of the XIII century - "Tretyce of Husbandry" - the requirements for the auditor were defined: he must be loyal and prudent, know his business. Accounting should be clear to everyone, so that it is possible to judge the size of profits and losses.

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